

The influence of urban development on the creation of Barcelona paradigm

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on studying the urban development and historical background of the city of Barcelona and the effects on urban and architectural fabric, and aims at monitoring the features of urban and architectural conversions and transformation of the city, taking into consideration the economic and social variables and city planning over time. It outlines the most important events that affect the urban and architectural pattern of this city. The city paradigm is an accumulation of multiple urban experiments and projects in the city throughout its history, and in most cases a city is a combination of the accomplishment of each planner, architect, stakeholder and citizen whether it is constructive or destructive to the structure of the city and its overall results. Although paradigm shift theory of Thomas Samuel Kuhn^① describes the paradigm as a type of thinking, and when the paradigm shift occurs, it comes as a revolution and new competing method to solve the problems, change the current system and create a new paradigm. This paper deals with Barcelona paradigm which may not be the perfect city paradigm around the world, but it is definitely an important example owing to a century and a half's continuation of urban development with an urban paradigm shifts, taking into consideration of the progress of the city structure, citizens' requirements and local, national and international issues.

Keywords: Catalonia, Barcelona, Universal exhibition, Cerda, Gaudi, Urban development, City vision

1 Introduction

Spain is a Mediterranean country with rich experiences and a variety of historical and contemporary developments in the sectors of tourism, urbanization, construction, and sustainable development. The Spanish experiences in developing urban planning and architecture design of the waterfront city are largely

depended on the development of coastal cities, since coastal cities are the waterfront of the state, and thus should be supported and developed, starting from the central government and down levels of planning to regional planning. Spanish local municipalities with the participation of both government and private sectors do work together to develop the urban planning and architecture design (PPP).

Post-independence Spain has 17 regions, and each region has many municipalities working within the vision of the government. Besides, the local sectors are the goals for each city. They base on the

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local economic, social and natural resources. Some cities have a heading board which creates plans under their supervision to ensure that their city will be the most important city and the first industrial touristic city in the country, with the special characteristics of the small Mediterranean city.

Catalonia is an independent region which has taken the lead in strategic investment in research and development in Spain, and successfully attracts research funds to the region from Spanish and European Union sources. Today Catalonia takes a large share of Spain's innovation activity resources, strong researches and infrastructure, and enjoys a higher share of the labor force with tertiary education compared with OECD² averages. (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2011)

Barcelona is the capital of Catalonia, and a leader in culture and creative industries and the field of universities and sciences. It is a growing business center and among one of the most attractive destinations in the world. Barcelona's example is an architectural showcase for both residents and tourists. Buildings are adorned with Modernism and Catalan version of Art Nouveau (Cahyadi, TenBrink, Barbosa, & Kursten, 2004).

1.1 General structural planning in Spain

Planning levels in Spain start from the governmental authority and the central government, followed by the regional authority, then the local authority and the municipalities (Table 1). The central government usually determines the outline for land use and acquisition methods of land, and then develops petition strategies for the whole country (natural resources and green spaces). The municipality is the responsible party for decision-making within the administrative borders.

The central government does not interfere with the work of the cities, although the general national law of Spain grants this right. It only interferes in the cases of important, vital and large projects such as coastal bend, airports, high speeds rails, facilities and the high-voltage lines. These vital projects receive their funding under the same management structure, according to the importance of the project, considering that tourism is the main source of financial revenue in Spain (Barcelona City Council, 2014).

Table 1. Planning levels in Spain.

The coastline of Spain is planned at the national level, particularly the protection and green areas, the built-up areas and the large vital projects of public interest. The role of national authorities complements the role of local authorities and municipalities, through the regional authorities, taking into account the large government projects sponsored by the government when making the decisions.

1.2 Waterfront and coast line planning at the regional level for Catalonia region

Planning prerogatives are distributed between the municipality and the planning authority in Catalonia. Spanish waterfront planning at the regional level is studied by dividing it into sectors on the entire coastline, each stage of which depends on general plans and frameworks underlying municipalities in urban planning and local operations in the municipalities of the coastal strip. Regional planning for Catalonia Coast has adopted a plan that emphasizes four important points: infrastructure, human settlements and communities, empty spaces and areas to be protected and occupancy³, in addition to maintaining important public scene and heritage areas (Hassan, 2007).

Fig. 1. The walled city of Barcelona and the pressure of urbanization.

Planning of Catalonia Coast is a plan that has been set to utilize the alternative energies and solar energy to supporting the coast, since the destruction of the coast demolishes the basis of tourist activity in the tourist area, and reduces the tourism income which constitutes a continuous income that cannot be stopped.

1.3 The historical status of the master plan of Barcelona

The shape of Barcelona is geographically limited between the sea, the surrounding mountains and two rivers. These positions limit the urban development and the access roads to Barcelona, which is the most important feature of Barcelona, and the most important problem as well, considering the difficulty of growing and of making a large urban expansion. It later gives the priority for the development of the coast with the possibility of maintaining and protecting the surrounding mountains.

During 1750 to 1850, the walled city of Barcelona suffered from severe overcrowding, unhealthy conditions, heavy pollution and poor transportation network (Fig. 1). There was simply no way for growth and urban development^④.

During 1854 to 1856, there was a brief Progressive rule in Spain, and the government authorized demolition of Barcelona's walls (Aibar & Bijker, 1997).

In 1855, the government commissioned from

a. Expansion project of Francesc Soler i Gloria in 1859.

b. Expansion project of Josep Fontserè i Mestre in 1859.

c. Expansion project of Miquel Garriga i Roca in 1859.

d. Expansion project of Antoni Rovira i Trias in 1859.

e. Expansion project of Ildefonso Cerdà in 1859.

Fig. 2. Some proposal plans of the competition.

Fig. 3. Barcelona urban development timeline during one century and a half.

Cerdà⁵ a topographical survey map of the outskirts, Cerdà found a New Discipline, and wrote the general theory of urbanization: the Science of Urbanization. In 1858, the competition of design the extension of Barcelona was held by the Barcelona government, with 13 participated designers (Mackay, 1989).

The city government awarded the design of the extension to the architect Antoni Rovira i Trias⁶. His design had a big square as a central point for the new street and many arcs with the same center around the old city, and employed classic architecture details. However, the central government in Madrid imposed Cerdà's plan (Eixample⁷) on the populace (Fig. 2).

Cerdà's innovative design aims to develop a modern Barcelona, and open city connection with the old city and other cities at the same time. The design was with a grid of wide streets, making primary element that blocks of dwellings with internal courtyards and street corners chambered with a 45 angle to facilitate traffic. As a result, the city started to have modern form and urban expanding image.

2 Methods

This paper uses documentary methods and data collection based on historical and academic documents and interviews with Barcelona municipality, stakeholders and local people. It contains a diagnosis of the situation during the exploratory mission to study the Spanish experience in seven Spanish cities with a focus on Barcelona as a case study.

The research concludes the basic aspects which impact significantly the value and the conversion of urban and architectural pattern of Barcelona during the recent 150 years.

2.1 The research problem and aims

These days, the city suffers from a lack of vision, and in general, the structural planning levels for the whole country have caused the lack of city identities.

Barcelona enjoys a wide international popularity, and has a flexible urban development that leads to radical changes in urban and architectural patterns which occurred several times in history influenced by political, cultural or social factors, etc. Reading the urban story of the city model can learn lessons as fundamentals for making great cities.

The paper aims to outline the accomplishments and experiences of planning and designing the city of Barcelona, so as to benefit from them to form the basic approach and methodology that can be applied in the development of local standards and visions in other cities of the similar kind. It emphasizes the necessity of having concept and city vision to maintain the memory and history of the city and to plan the city's future according to its criteria, the local and global changes, new theories and materials.

3 Results and factors of Barcelona's urban development

The analysis of the changes in urban and architectural fabric of this city and reconstruction that happened several times of Barcelona, is considered as an ideal model for the change and paradigm shift, owing to political and economic factors, social mobility, individual creativity of local architects, and the pyramidal planning structure of the city which starts from central government down to the municipality when forming the visions, development strategies and projects.

Fig. 4. The role of Ildefons Cerdà in the modern planning of modern Barcelona.

The four universal events of Barcelona have contributed to the change of its city image throughout time. From the discussions we can summarize the results and factors of Barcelona's urban development during the recent 150 years (Fig. 3).

3.1 Individual creativity: Spanish architects and planners

The competition of 1858, in addition to other real competitions among the urban planners and developers in Barcelona aiming to achieve the expansion, as well as providing the scientific and experimental background and visions for the individual creativity of Spanish architects and planners, especially Cerdà and Gaudí, played an important role in creating the identity of Barcelona—a modern and different city.

Cerdà with his five bases of the general theory of urbanization (Puig, 1999) tries to establish a comprehensive, integrative approach for urban planning to create a new city as a metropolitan area by thinking of Barcelona's future after the industry revolution. He plans to connect the surrounding towns to the main city and increasing the availability of land, and adapt the city to meet the new needs of transport, networks and expansion, and the essential

requirements of the new industrial city with sewage disposal systems, adaption of new steam power (steam trains and cars) with new infrastructure, and the railway network which is on a level separate from the streets. Extension is also based on the study of green zones, streets network, intersections, and housing groups which determines the size and shape in the proposed models of Cerdà (Cerdà, 2013) (Fig. 4).

The Catalan architect Antoni Gaudí[®] utilizes oriental techniques, modern and organic style inspired by natural forms. He usually uses colored glass, cycled ceramic, and ironworks. Many unique parks and buildings with a distinctive architectural style designed by Gaudí have appeared in some parts of the city according to Cerdà master plan, such as Park Güell, Casa Batlló, unfinished church Sagrada Família in 1882, etc. (Fig. 5). Seven of Gaudí's works have been listed in world heritage list after 1984. Barcelona gradually develops a special feature as a modern city with Catalan identity.

3.2 The first international event (The universal exposition of 1888)

Barcelona started to be differentiated from the rest of the Spanish State by its socio-economic situation after its industrial growth and cultural

Fig. 5. Gaudí's works.

progress, and Barcelona government made efforts to pursue a new and developed city by establishing the universal exposition of 1888 for Catalan industrial products in a big park which was despised by the Barcelonans due to the punishment for crimes and prison throughout the nineteenth century, so as to erase bad memory and start new period (Lees & Lees, 2007) (Fig. 6).

The Exposition was held in the Ciutadella Park. Barcelona was portrayed as a bourgeoisie and industrial city on an international level. The Exposition employed new ways to attract people with activities such as electric lighting in the city for the first time, the Captive Balloon and memorial speech about the importance of Barcelona as the Columbus Monument and its lions, in addition to many museums, panoramic buildings and pavilions to present city science, arts, industry and agriculture, maritime exhibition (Niето-Galan, 2012).

3.3 The second international event (The universal exhibition of 1929)

The previous 1888 Exposition had led to a great advance in the economic, architectural and technological growth and development of the city. Therefore, a new exhibition in the early 1900s was proposed to highlight the city's further technological progress and increase the awareness outside the

Fig. 6. The universal exposition of 1888.

modern Catalan industry (Fig. 7). It was an Exhibition of Electric Industries and Their "Applications", and urban planning of Montjuïc and its adjacent areas and the renovation of public spaces was required. A funicular was built to allow access to the top of the mountain, and aerial tram was constructed to connect the mountain with the Port of Barcelona. However, the aerial tram did not open until after the fair in 1931. They also allowed for the construction of several emblematic buildings and structures, as well as many pavilions as Barcelona Pavilion that were designed by German Bauhaus architect Ludwig Mies van der Rohe.

The Exposition originally planned for 1917, but it finally took place in 1929 due to World War I and the delay of construction. It required the change of the goal to include three aspects (industry, sports, art). Apart from the relative success of the Exhibition, it was also a great success at the social level as it allowed for a large influx of people and achievements for the city of Barcelona, especially in the fields of architecture and urbanism.

The both universal industrial exhibitions of 1888 and 1929 changed the city image and showed the development of the industrial city and working waterfront city. But during the fifty years of industry that spread in Barcelona, the city waterfront looked like an industrial working waterfront and started to lose its identity (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. The universal exhibition of 1929.

Fig. 8. Barcelona waterfront in the late 1970s.

3.4 Rehabilitation of the waterfront

After Spanish civil war, Barcelona received a huge number of immigrants, which gave economic power for work and investment. The migrations and the unregulated expansion that happened outside the city's administrative boundaries caused a random housing and human settlement. The coastline and the harbor area were the contact point between the city and the sea, and were used as the unload area of cargo ships with railway. Thus, the coastline character became industrial character, which led to its inclusion in master plan in 1950 identified as an industrial zone.

Influenced by the democratic system in Spain, the regulation plan of 1976 tried to organize the city's growth and the development of standards for new construction, and led to the modern process of construction and development, as well as the development of standards of life in Barcelona to attract investment.

The regulation plan of studying the land use to create a new free interface was approved. The rehabilitation of the waterfront started by moving the rail train to another place of the city between 1989-1992, and taking the train down underground. Then the rehabilitation of the harbor and its buildings was made, followed by a series of rehabilitation processes to extend to the entire coastline of Barcelona, according to sequential stages (Fig. 9).

The construction and rehabilitation of the seaside continued on the beaches and harbor. They constructed the underground train without removing

the industrial areas, instead, remaining them for people to swim at the same time. Later, they transferred the industrial areas in the waterfront outside the zone, and replaced it with administrative functions and advanced industries and technology.

The city council gave the design process to the architects and distinct architectural competitions to design coastline pilot projects, in order to build an architectural uniqueness waterfront. The coastal part of Barcelona consists of three main components: the city mid-high urban vocabulary, the harbor area and agricultural area outside the city.

3.5 Rehabilitation and rebuilding the old city of Barcelona

The purposes of this project was to reconnect the old city with the whole city, and to add the old city new value as needed for high tech industries by converting the current urban fabric and changing the land use.

The implementation of infrastructure happened within a single step, but the rehabilitation and rebuilding of the blocks had been in different forms and times, taking into account the importance of the historical buildings and the architectural integrations for the traditional activities, multifunction, commercial and residential development (Fig. 10). For example, la Rambla was a very poor area in the old city, and had been completely converted into a tourist and commercial area, which led to the creation of investment in the area and employment opportunities

Fig. 9. The coastline of Barcelona.

Fig. 10. Historical and new building in the old city.

Fig. 11. Barcelona waterfront.

for people living nearby.

The old buildings and distinctive architectural vocabulary were not only located in the old city, but also extended to the outside and the coastline, which contributed to the formation of Waterfront Barcelona together with new one.

3.6 The third international event (The Barcelona Olympic Games in 1992)

The goal was the construction of the Olympic Village, which was completed in 1992 in the coastal part of the city to rehabilitate and improve the waterfront and integrate it with the rest of the city, as well as develop other parts of the coastal area. The construction and development process was relied on a public and private sector partnership supported by the central and local governments (Montaner, 2011).

Many new projects were built as the Olympic Port, including the twin towers of the Arts Hotel and Mapfre tower which was the tallest buildings in Spain at that time, the renovated seafront as Barceloneta beach, Olympic Stadium buildings, the Palace of Sant Jordi, Golden Fish of Frank Gehry and Santiago Calatrava's Telefonica Tower to transmit TV coverage of the Games (Fig. 11).

In spite of the huge cost of public investment on the subsequent new roads and undergrounds when developing the road network in waterfront design, these new forms of transportation raised property values and made the waterfront a place for wandering and strolling to the city center. The positive impact of the Olympics on the city was a long-term success. This event raised the local Catalan pride, business confidence in the city, availability of services and

Fig. 12. The Universal Forum of Cultures 2004.

market, and its competitiveness. As a result, Barcelona got the good rank as one of the most visited cities among the European cities of the 1990s behind London, Paris and Rome (i Cid, 2005).

3.7 The fourth international event (The Universal Forum of Cultures in 2004)

The Universal Forum of Cultures was held in Barcelona for the first time as an international cultural event intended to take place every three years in collaboration with UNESCO and commercial sponsorship by multinationals (Fig. 12). This event was organized to promote the city's growing tourist industry after 1992 Olympics, and continued for 141 days of activities based on three theme axis: sustainable development, conditions for peace and cultural diversity (Fòrum Barcelona 2004, 2004).

To achieve the goal of sustainability in Barcelona, the focus was on having environmental friendly infrastructures and systems by modernizing the infrastructures and creating an underground water treatment plant and generation electrical energy plant as well as solar plates (Fig. 13), and integrated them in a new urban waterfront including many symbolic buildings such as the Forum Building and the International Convention Centre (Ivancic, 2015).

Barcelona started to suffer from the lack of green areas because of urbanization pressure. The spread of green spaces was very necessary, and the ornamental plants in the balconies and roofs became insufficient. Thus, they tried to create a large green space near the huge Agbar Tower[®], and also to mitigate accidents and risks of traffic. They created a new infrastructure in 15 hectares of areas located in a neighborhood (La

Fig. 13. Underground water treatment plant and generation electrical energy plant and solar plates.

Fig. 14. La Sagrera project with underground transport networks.

Sagrera, Fig. 14) consisting of residential units, hotels, offices and underground transport networks of the bus, metro, high speed trains and parking, so that it

Fig. 15. The human dimension in urban planning.

Fig. 16. Urban integration in Barcelona to achieve the knowledge economy.

secured gardens and wider or more greater places for pedestrians in the healthy environment.

With the new mobility, green infrastructure, waste collection system and sustainable strategies which focusing on human dimension in urban planning (Fig. 15), in addition to the important urban projects and the two international events of 1992 and 2004, urbanism and the image and vision of the city have changed to make Barcelona as a tourist, smart and sustainable city.

Fig. 17. Barcelona Biomedical Research Park.

3.8 Knowledge economy

After the global changes in the visions and needs according to the new issues, the role of knowledge, science, technology and human capital has become the basic key in the development of the economy and the progress of society to achieve sustainable development in new ways, to reduce dependence on exhaustible resources such as oil and ensure sustainable future of the country (Piqué, 2012).

Barcelona employs contemporary and advanced strategies, new goals and new vision that commensurate with the current digital and technological era as well as new theories and building materials, while takes into account the local and international changes and criteria to achieve the knowledge economy (Marquet & Miralles-Guascha, 2015).

Barcelona municipality defines the bad condition and dilapidated areas in the back urban fabric of the waterfront to create urban integration, and develops innovation district to develop science and universities (Fig. 16). Many projects have been built under this vision as the project of Barcelona biomedical research park (Fig. 17), media-TIC building and the new university campus (The Spiral Tower).

4 Conclusion

Barcelona waterfront city has the contemporary and future designs that can be taken as an inspiration to form methods in other cities. This city has witnessed many economic and social and cultural transformations which requires a change in the methods and the way of thinking to solve the problems and achieve paradigm shift. It is a good

example of city paradigm with many paradigm shifts that changed according to the new requirements, which can be interpreted by the city image and scene.

Paradigm of Barcelona is an accumulation of the individualism of creative Catalan architects and planners, the state authority, flexible city master plan and building code, in addition to the change of the city concept and the coastline functions with creative universal events and pilot projects to support each vision to develop the city urbanism started from the walled city to an industrial city, then from touristic city to the smart and sustainable city, then down to the knowledge economy city.

Notes

- ① Thomas Samuel Kuhn is the author of the book “The Structure of Scientific Revolutions”. He is an American physicist, historian, and philosopher of science.
- ② OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) is an international economic organization of 34 countries founded in 1961 to stimulate economic progress and world trade.
- ③ The compression of urbanization, in addition to the pressure caused by transport and harbor in the coastal strip led to the reduction of the sandy beach of the coast of Catalonia, which led to the need for the territorial division of the region and that by dividing it into sectors on the entire coastal strip, according to the following percentages: (46% urban areas of the coast of Catalonia, 40% areas protected from the urban planning, building and construction permissions has been stopped for a certain limit, but the owners have development rights in it, 6% areas where the building permissions are possible, 8% areas still for urban development that has not been not yet. (The third and fourth Areas do not have the rights of urban development but will announce a licensing while preserving as much as possible on the beach), (Government of Catalonia Department of Territorial Policy, Spain (09 18, 2007)).
- ④ At the beginning of the industrial revolution at the beginning of the 19th century in western European countries.
- ⑤ Ildefons Cerdà is a Catalan Spanish urban planner and civil engineer (was born in Centelles in 1815, and died in 1876). He was also interested in politics, and became an elected member of the Cortes (parliament) in 1850; many of the Catalan architects of his time opposed Cerdà’s ideas, even accusing him of promoting socialism,

when Cerdà's design prevailed, the major property owners were angry. His major works and theories: Theory of City Construction and the plan of the extension of Barcelona, 1859- Theory of Urban Road Space and Reform of That of Madrid, 1861- Theory of the Linkage of movement on Land ways and Seaways, 1863- General Theory of Urbanization, 1867- General Theory of Ruralization.

- ⑥ Antoni Rovira i Trias is a Catalan architect, urban planner, and founder of several associations. He designed several buildings in Barcelona (was born in Barcelona in 1816, and died in 1889).
- ⑦ The Catalan word "Eixample" means the extension.
- ⑧ Antoni Gaudí (was born in 1852, and died in 1926) is a Catalan architect. The classifications of his works are Catalan Modernism and Neo-Gothic art, seven of which were declared World Heritage Sites by UNESCO. Gaudí's religious and faith during his life appeared in many of his works, and led people to call him "God's Architect".
- ⑨ Agbar Tower is designed by French architect Jean Nouvel who inspired from Gaudí's works. The skin of the tower has temperature and humidity sensors connected with a computer system regulating the consumption of energy required for heating and cooling system.

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References

- Aibar, E. & Bijker, W. E. (1997). Constructing a city: The Cerda plan for the extension of Barcelona. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 22(1), 3-30.
- Barcelona City Council (2014). *White Paper Barcelona, the capital of a new state*. Retrieved from http://barcelonallibres.bcn.cat/sites/default/files/publicacions_fitxers/libreblanc_totred72ok.pdf
- Cahyadi, G., TenBrink, S., Barbosa, C. & Kursten, B. (2004). *Barcelona Metropolitan Economic Strategy*. Retrieved from Global urban development: <http://www.globalurban.org/GUD%20Barcelona%20MES%20Report.pdf>
- Cerdà, I. (2013). Retrieved from Generalitat de Catalunya: http://empresaiocupacio.gencat.cat/web/.content/20_-_turisme/publicacions/documents/arxius/doc_38235229_1.pdf
- Fòrum Barcelona 2004. (2010, 3 14). Retrieved from Fòrum Barcelona 2004: <http://www.barcelona2004.org/www.barcelona2004.org/cat/forum2004.htm>
- Hassan, M. (2007). The Spanish experience in each of: Waterfront urban planning, human dimension in the traffic system in both of coastal cities (Barcelona and Alicante). Tartous, Syria: Tartous municipality.
- i Cid, F. B. (2005). *The economic impact of the Barcelona Olympic Games, 1986-2004/Barcelona: the legacy of the Games 1992-2002/*. Retrieved from The Olympic Studies Centre: http://olympicstudies.uab.es/pdf/wp084_eng.pdf
- Ivancic, A. (2015). *District Heating and Cooling: an opportunity for profiting from local energy sources -3 case studies*. Retrieved from Université de Genève: <http://www.cuepe.ch/html/enseigne/pdf/trp-12-13-13.pdf>
- Lees, A. & Lees, L. H. (2007). *Cities and the making of modern Europe, 1750-1914*. Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Mackay, D. (1989). *Modern Architecture in Barcelona 1854-1939*. New York, USA: Rizzoli.
- Marquet, O. & Miralles-Guascha, C. (2015). The walkable city and the importance of the proximity environments for Barcelona's everyday mobility. *Cities*, 42(Part B), 258-266.
- Montaner, J. M. (2011). The Barcelona model reviewed: leading up to 1992 Olympic Games, "Learning from Barcelona: art, real estate and the pre-olympic city a dialogue between London and Barcelona".
- Nieto-Galan, A. (2012). Scientific "marvels" in the public sphere: Barcelona and its 1888 International Exhibition. *Journal of History of Science and Technology*, 6, 33-63.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2011). *Higher Education in Regional and City Development: Catalonia, Spain 2011*. Paris, France: OECD Publishing. Retrieved from <http://www.oecd.org/edu/imhe/46827358.pdf>.
- Puig, A. S. (1999). Cerda: the Five Bases of the General Theory of Urbanization. Madrid, Spain: Electa.
- Piqué, J. M. (2012). *Knowledge Cities on Smart Cities: 22@Barcelona Case*. Retrieved from United Nations Economic Commission for Europe: http://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/ceci/documents/2012/ICP/TOS_ICP/Pique.pdf